

Analysing the public's beliefs, emotions and sentiments towards Metaverse workplace: A big-data qualitative inquiry

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ABSTRACT

The Metaverse is gaining attention as a potential future workplace, and advancements in VR/AR technologies are set to revolutionise how we work and collaborate. Extensive research using big data is still needed to fully comprehend the public's perception of this emerging field. Grounded in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT), and Social Presence Theory (SPT), this study seeks to fill this knowledge gap. Using a methodology that involved machine learning and qualitative analysis of big data, the research gathered comments from social media users on widely viewed YouTube videos discussing the Metaverse workplace. The initial dataset, which contained 6982 comments, underwent thorough cleaning processes, resulting in the analysis of 2804 comments through thematic, emotion, and sentiment analyses. The process of the thematic analysis revealed that out of the total comments, 472 were unclassified, while the remaining 2332 helped structure the public's beliefs about the Metaverse workplace into four overarching themes: 1- benefits of flexibility and accessibility (37 %), highlighting VR's potential to transform workspaces, especially for creative fields and efficient space use; 2- Health concerns (26 %), including eye strain and physical discomfort from prolonged headset use; 3- data privacy and corporate control fears (20 %), reflecting worries over pervasive data collection and potential misuse of power; 4- scepticism over readiness and practicality (17 %), noting visual clarity challenges and ergonomic issues. The overall vibes about working in the Metaverse are mixed. While more than half the sentiments were positive, expressing contentment, curiosity and enthusiasm, there were also concerns about health effects, data privacy, and integration issues. The public recognises Metaverse's potential for remote work, desiring improvements in areas like visual clarity, ergonomics and productivity support before widespread adoption. This study is a pioneering effort in the field, providing a first-of-its-kind structure of the public's beliefs about the Metaverse workplace, drawing upon naturally occurring data. The findings not only contribute to the academic understanding of the Metaverse workplace but also have significant implications for society and practitioners for optimising the positive aspects to enhance overall acceptance in this relatively understudied field.

1. Introduction

The *Metaverse Workplace* market is projected to grow from a value of US\$4.9bn in 2024 to US\$27.7bn by 2030, with a CAGR of 33.43 %, driven by the increasing adoption of virtual collaboration and remote work solutions, especially in the United States where the market is expected to reach US\$1537 m in 2024 (Statista Market Insights, 2023). The Metaverse workplace is a 3D virtual immersive environment where employees interact through avatar identities, perform work tasks, and have autonomy and opportunities for creativity (Šimová, Zychová, & Fejfarová, 2023). This digital space, i.e. the Metaverse, connects

communities, products, services, content creators, entertainment, e-commerce, and real-world elements, providing a shared and enduring environment (Jaber, 2022). Workplace design in the Metaverse is crucial for firms' digital transformation, with research focusing on effective workspace design criteria and evaluating different Metaverse platforms (Erik, Kuvvetli, Kuvvetli, & Hamidy, 2023). However, broader societal concerns have emerged, particularly those related to VR and the Metaverse (Dincelli & Yayla, 2022). Issues such as data privacy, corporate control, and the ethical implications of these technologies have sparked significant debate (Egliston & Carter, 2021).

The Metaverse workplace harnesses advanced technologies like

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blockchain, augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), extended reality (XR), smart contracts, and more (Jim, Hosain, Mridha, Kabir, & Shin, 2023; Mahmoud, 2023). These cutting-edge tools and systems fundamentally transform work dynamics, enabling immersive experiences, decentralised operations, and sophisticated digital interactions, shaping the evolution of work environments (Shrier, 2023). Notwithstanding, the emergence of the Metaverse as a workplace is not occurring in a vacuum but is influenced by broader societal attitudes towards technology (Dincelli & Yayla, 2022). This is particularly evident in the growing 'techlash'—a backlash against the overreach of technology companies. As Messeri (2024) highlights in *In the Land of the Unreal*, this techlash reflects a deep-seated scepticism and caution among the public, shaped by past experiences with technology, making this context crucial for understanding the varied responses to the Metaverse, from enthusiasm to scepticism and demands for accountability.

The adoption of the Metaverse workplace has significant economic implications, as it can lead to cost savings for organisations through reduced office space requirements and increased productivity from remote work (Darvish, Keresztyen, & Bick, 2023; Gesing, 2024; Šimová et al., 2023). However, it also raises managerial challenges, such as the need to adapt leadership styles and communication strategies for virtual environments (Mahmoud, Berman, Reisel, Fuxman, & Hack-Polay, 2024; Poore, 2023). Equally important, ensuring both the psychological well-being of employees and equity among them in the Metaverse is an emerging priority, emphasising the necessity for inclusive policies and practices that support mental health (Rosioru, 2023; Zallio & Clarkson, 2022). From a policy perspective, the Metaverse workplace may require new regulations to address issues of data privacy, worker rights, and digital inequality (Caragnano, 2023; Marabelli & Newell, 2023).

Given this backdrop, understanding the public's beliefs and attitudes towards the Metaverse workplace becomes even more critical. This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap centred on this and offer a first-of-its-kind structure of beliefs the public has developed about the Metaverse workplace. Therefore, this study is set to portray the public's beliefs and sentiments towards the Metaverse workplace. To achieve this goal, the study utilises rigorous big-data methodology and machine-learning techniques to analyse comments from popular YouTube videos discussing various aspects of the workplace in the Metaverse that can be of interest to the public like *enhancement of work environment, digital workspaces evolution* and their *ethical considerations*, etc. Our use of big data analysis, which involves advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms, allows us to uncover hidden patterns and correlations that can deepen our understanding of public beliefs and attitudes (Chen, 2022). Moreover, big data analysis provides real-time insights into public sentiment and beliefs through its ability to capture unstructured data such as social media posts and online discussions (Geissinger, Laurell, Öberg, & Sandström, 2023). Big data analysis allows for the exploration of vast datasets to uncover patterns and trends in public opinions, enabling firms to tailor their digital transformation initiatives to align with societal expectations and preferences (Singh & Glińska-Noweś, 2022). Furthermore, the study draws on established theories such as Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Rogers's (2010) Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT) and Short, Williams, and Christie's (1976) Social Presence Theory (SPT) as theoretical underpinnings to interpret the results.

That said, the study is, therefore, guided by the following research questions:

1. What do people generally believe about the Metaverse workplace?
2. What are the accompanying emotions and sentiments expressed in public discourse regarding the Metaverse workplace?

Answering these questions is relevant to firms undergoing digital transformation for several reasons. Understanding public perceptions can provide valuable insights into the acceptance and adoption of

Metaverse technologies within organisational settings, influencing the strategic implementation of these initiatives Zhang, Li, and Xie (2023). Public sentiments towards the Metaverse workplace can impact innovation investment volatility, supply chain resilience, and corporate sustainability, highlighting the interconnectedness between public perceptions and firm outcomes (Sun & He, 2023; Yin, 2022; Zhang, Chen, & Chen, 2022). Moreover, exploring the public's beliefs can shed light on the potential barriers or facilitators to digital transformation, guiding firms in leveraging digital technologies effectively to enhance performance and sustainability (Fuxia, Lin, & Zhai, 2022; Zhao, Meng, Wang, Alam, & Zhang, 2023). For example, suppose the public expresses concerns about data privacy in the Metaverse workplace. In that case, firms may need to prioritise robust security measures and transparent data handling practices to build trust and facilitate adoption (e.g. Jim et al., 2023). Similarly, if the public perceives the Metaverse workplace as enhancing flexibility and accessibility, firms can leverage these beliefs to promote the benefits of virtual work environments and attract talent (e.g. Rozak, Fachrunnisa, Sugiharti, & Fitriati, 2023). To ensure that digital transformation strategies align with society's expectations, companies can analyse the public's views on Metaverse workplaces. This approach enables firms to adopt more inclusive and responsive technological advancements (Kim, Choi, & Lew, 2021; Wu, Wang, Lu, Ma, & Gao, 2023). Therefore, taking into account the prevailing public sentiments and addressing them appropriately, organisations can devise Metaverse workplace strategies that can not only lead to business success but also contribute positively to social welfare and employee well-being. Ultimately, public sentiments towards the Metaverse workplace can serve as a barometer for firms seeking to navigate the evolving digital landscape and capitalise on the opportunities presented by digital transformation (Tran, Thu, Huan, & Trung, 2022).

After this introduction, the paper reviews the literature surrounding the Metaverse workplace and the foundational theories. It then proceeds to describe the research methodology and present the findings of the thematic, emotional, and sentiment analyses. Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion of the implications and limitations of the study.

2. Literature review

2.1. Metaverse workplace

The COVID-19 pandemic dramatically accelerated the transformation of work settings, highlighting the limitations of physical offices and traditional remote work solutions (Mahmoud, Berman, et al., 2024; Mitchell, 2023). Against this backdrop, the Metaverse emerged as a promising frontier, offering innovative dimensions for remote working through the creation of virtual spaces that replicate or enhance physical office environments (Al-Ghaili et al., 2022; Orel, 2022; Polyviou & Pappas, 2023). Utilising virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies, the Metaverse facilitates immersive and interactive workspaces, fostering a sense of presence and belonging among remote employees and addressing the challenge of physical disconnection (Koochang et al., 2023; Lemmens & von Münchhausen, 2023; Park, Ahn, & Lee, 2023; Poore, 2023).

Building on this technological foundation, the design and customisation of virtual offices in the Metaverse gained prominence as organisations sought adaptable and resilient work environments (Hack-Polay et al., 2023; Pandey, Grima, Pandey, & Balusamy, 2024; Park et al., 2023). The pandemic spurred the need for office designs that reflect organisational culture while enhancing creativity and productivity, with ergonomic and environmental considerations ensuring employee well-being (Mikus, Rieger, & Grant-Smith, 2022; Mohezar, Jaafar, & Akbar, 2021). This adaptability offers opportunities for creating more inclusive work environments that cater to diverse employee needs, but it also requires careful navigation of virtual space design to avoid creating disorienting or exclusionary environments (Baker, 2022).

However, the rapid adoption of these technologies presents significant challenges for firms, including substantial initial investments, the need for continuous technological upgrades, and the potential for a widened digital divide among workers based on access and proficiency with these technologies (Ciarli, Kenney, Massini, & Piscitello, 2021; De Giovanni, 2023; Lythreathis, Singh, & El-Kassar, 2022; Shakina, Parshakov, & Alsufiev, 2021). Technical and accessibility barriers, such as hardware requirements and digital literacy, became more apparent with the rapid shift to virtual work environments and Metaverse workplaces (Goodall-Monk, 2023; Jagatheesaperumal, Ahmad, Al-Fuqaha, & Qadir, 2024; Zallio & Clarkson, 2022). Moreover, public concerns about these issues, coupled with the broader scepticism captured by the techlash phenomenon, highlight the need for critical engagement with the societal implications of these technologies (Messeri, 2024). Privacy, security, and ethical concerns, including data protection and virtual harassment, require careful consideration to ensure a safe and respectful virtual workplace in the Metaverse (Marabelli & Lirio, 2024; Renieris, 2023; Wylde, Prakash, Hewage, & Platts, 2023). These challenges emphasise the need for robust governance frameworks and ethical guidelines to protect users in the Metaverse, balancing innovation with safeguarding individual rights and well-being.

Simultaneously, employee engagement and experience have also been redefined in the pandemic and post-pandemic eras (Even & Christiansen, 2023; Mer & Srivastava, 2023; Panneerselvam & Balaraman, 2022). Organisations increasingly turned to the Metaverse to host virtual events, workshops, and interactive learning experiences, which became essential for employee satisfaction and retention during periods of remote work (Al-Ghaili et al., 2022; Bawany, 2023; Koochang et al., 2023; Pandey et al., 2024). However, the challenge of maintaining work-life balance in the immersive Metaverse environment necessitated innovative strategies to prevent burnout and ensure healthy work-life integration (Mahmoud, Reisel, Hack-Polay, & Fuxman, 2021; Reilly, 2022).

In addition to these considerations, the pandemic's impact on collaboration and communication further emphasised the need for effective virtual tools (Colenberg, Appel-Meulenbroek, Romero Herrera, & Keyson, 2021; Riva, Aureli, & Silvestrini, 2022; Weinberg & Hausfeld, 2024). The Metaverse responded by providing advanced collaboration tools that support real-time interaction, brainstorming, and project management, enhancing teamwork across global teams working in Metaverse environments (Chamakiotis, Panteli, & Davison, 2021; Popescu, Ciurlău, Stan, Băcănoiu, & Tănase, 2022). These tools have become essential, particularly during extreme contexts like the pandemic, as they enable seamless collaboration and help maintain productivity despite global disruptions (Mahmoud, Berman, et al., 2024; Waizenegger, McKenna, Cai, & Bendz, 2020). Yet, firms must navigate the complexities of ensuring data privacy and security within these collaborative platforms, balancing the benefits of open and dynamic work environments against the risks of data breaches and cyber threats.

While previous research provides some insights into the initial reception and potential benefits of Metaverse-based work, it does not fully account for the public beliefs, emotions, and sentiments over the long term. Our study aims to fill these critical gaps by using a sophisticated big-data approach, making significant contributions to both academic discussions and practical implementations in the evolving field of workplace technology.

2.2. Acceptance of the metaverse beyond the workplace

While the Metaverse workplace offers exciting possibilities (Marabelli & Lirio, 2024), its adoption can be influenced by broader societal perceptions and acceptance of Metaverse technology. The growing techlash reflects a deep-seated scepticism and caution among the public towards new technologies shaped by past experiences (Messeri, 2024). This backlash against the overreach of technology companies can significantly impact how different populations may

accept or reject the Metaverse (Renieris, 2023; Wheeler, 2023).

Moreover, ethical, privacy, and control concerns surrounding the Metaverse (Egliston & Carter, 2021; Maghaydah, Al-Emran, Maheshwari, & Al-Sharafi, 2024) further complicate its acceptance beyond the workplace. The potential for data misuse, surveillance, and corporate control in immersive virtual environments raises important questions about individual rights and well-being (Bibri & Allam, 2022). These societal-level concerns can influence individual attitudes and behaviours towards the Metaverse, affecting its diffusion and adoption across various domains (Mahmoud, 2024b). Thus, examining the Metaverse through this wider lens can provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities for its responsible development and integration into professional and personal spheres.

2.3. Theoretical foundations

This study's exploration of public beliefs about the Metaverse workplace is grounded in the integration of three fundamental theories: Davis's (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Rogers's (2010) Diffusion of Innovations Theory (DIT), and Short et al.'s (1976) Social Presence Theory (SPT). These theories offer distinct yet complementary perspectives on technology adoption, providing a robust framework for understanding the complex dynamics of Metaverse workplace acceptance.

With its focus on perceived usefulness and ease of use, TAM offers insights into individual-level decision-making regarding the adoption of virtual work environments (Davis, 1989). It suggests that if individuals view the Metaverse as enhancing productivity and being user-friendly, they are more inclined to embrace and promote its application in professional settings (e.g. Feng et al., 2020; Marabelli & Lirio, 2024; Park et al., 2023). In the context of the Metaverse workplace, TAM can help explain how factors such as the perceived benefits of virtual collaboration, the intuitiveness of the user interface, and the overall user experience shape employees' willingness to adopt this new technology (e.g. FakhrHosseini et al., 2024; Okoro, Nnaji, & Adediran, 2023; Thanomsing & Sharma, 2024). TAM's strength lies in its ability to predict individual acceptance based on cognitive assessments (Marangunić & Granić, 2015), a key factor in understanding initial Metaverse adoption (Mahmoud, 2024b; Mahmoud, Fuxman, Asaad, & Solakis, 2024).

However, this model's emphasis on cognitive processes may overlook the complex web of social, cultural, psychological, and organisational factors that also play a crucial role in technology acceptance (e.g. Brock & Khan, 2017; Kamal, Shafiq, & Kakria, 2020). For instance, organisational culture, leadership support, and peer influence can significantly impact employees' attitudes towards the Metaverse workplace beyond their individual perceptions of usefulness and ease of use (e.g. Besson & Gauthier, 2024; Pandey et al., 2024).

In contrast, DIT provides a macroscopic lens, examining the spread of new technologies across societies (Rogers, 2010). DIT's value lies in its ability to explain the broader societal and organisational contexts that influence technology adoption (Wejnert, 2002), complementing TAM's individual-level focus. According to Rogers (2010), this framework emphasises the characteristics of innovations, the structure of social systems, and the influence of opinion leaders, which collectively shape the trajectory of technology adoption. Applied to the Metaverse workplace, DIT stresses the importance of compatibility with existing work practices and the visibility of benefits in determining the technology's uptake among broader populations (e.g. Besson & Gauthier, 2024; Dia, 2023; Sharma, Dwivedi, Metri, Lal, & Elbanna, 2023). DIT can help explain how the Metaverse workplace's alignment with current remote work trends, its potential to enhance collaboration and productivity, and the endorsement by influential figures in the tech industry can drive its diffusion across organisations and industries (e.g. De Giovanni, 2023; Fåbeng & Royrhus, 2023). DIT's strength is its ability to capture the social dynamics and communication channels that influence the spread of innovations (Miller, 2015), providing insights into how Metaverse

technologies might gain traction in various professional contexts.

SPT, with its potential practical implications in the Metaverse workplace (Srivastava & Chandra, 2018; Zhang, Cao, Liu, & Qi, 2022), complements TAM and DIT by addressing the affective and relational dimensions. This theory posits that the degree of social presence, or the sense of being with others, facilitated by a communication medium can significantly influence user satisfaction and engagement (Short et al., 1976). In the context of the Metaverse, a high social presence can enhance virtual interactions, making employees feel more connected and engaged despite physical distance (Bleakley et al., 2022; Chen, 2023). This relational aspect is crucial for understanding how the Metaverse can impact teamwork, collaboration, and overall workplace dynamics (Orel, 2022; Šimová et al., 2023). SPT adds value by focusing on the quality of interpersonal interactions in virtual environments (Kehrwald, 2008), an aspect not directly addressed by TAM or DIT (Buck, Rieser, Narasimham, & Bodenheimer, 2019; Freeman & Acena, 2021; Raji et al., 2007) but critical for the success of Metaverse workplaces.

That said, integrating these theoretical perspectives offers a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play in the adoption of the Metaverse as a workplace. While TAM and DIT capture the psychological aspects of technology use and the broader social context within which these individual decisions are made, SPT adds depth by considering the relational and emotional dimensions (Short et al., 1976). This holistic approach recognises that the acceptance of the Metaverse workplace is not solely the outcome of individual appraisals but is also deeply influenced by social trends, cultural norms, and endorsement by key influencers. Indeed, by combining these theories, we can better account for the cognitive, social, and affective factors that collectively shape the adoption and diffusion of Metaverse technologies in professional settings.

However, the current study aims to extend and challenge these established theories in several ways. First, by examining public beliefs and sentiments through the lens of social media discourse, this research shifts the focus from controlled organisational settings to the broader societal context. This approach allows for an extended understanding of how public beliefs, emotions and sentiments, shaped by diverse experiences and perspectives, influence the adoption and diffusion of the Metaverse workplace. Specifically, capturing the authentic voices of individuals across various demographics and backgrounds is expected to expand the scope of TAM and DIT, highlighting the importance of considering public opinion as a critical factor in technology acceptance and diffusion.

Second, the study's emphasis on the emotional dimensions of public discourse challenges the predominantly cognitive focus of TAM (e.g. Davis & Granić, 2024). This approach recognises that technology acceptance is not solely driven by rational assessments of usefulness and ease of use but is also influenced by emotional responses, such as excitement, curiosity, fear, and scepticism (e.g. Mahmoud, 2024b). Therefore, by integrating these affective dimensions, the current study is expected to extend TAM by offering a more comprehensive understanding of the psychological factors that drive technology adoption.

Third, the study's focus on the Metaverse workplace, an emerging and rapidly evolving technology, pushes the boundaries of DIT. While DIT provides a valuable framework for understanding the diffusion of innovations, it has primarily been applied to established technologies with clear use cases and benefits (Mahmoud, Fuxman, et al., 2024). The Metaverse workplace, however, is still in its early stages (Šimová et al., 2023), with its potential applications and implications yet to be fully realised (Marabelli & Lirio, 2024). With the aim of examining public beliefs, emotions and sentiments about this emerging technology, the current study is set to contribute to the ongoing development of DIT, exploring how the theory can be adapted and refined to account for the unique challenges and opportunities presented by the Metaverse workplace.

Fourth, the study is expected to contribute to the SPT by exploring

how the sense of presence and social connection in the Metaverse workplace is believed to affect user engagement and satisfaction. Traditionally, SPT has been applied to more conventional communication media (e.g. Rice, 1993; Weidlich, Göksün, & Kreijns, 2023), such that by examining the Metaverse, this study pushes the boundaries of the theory, highlighting how enhanced social presence in virtual environments can influence work dynamics, team collaboration, and individual well-being. That is to say, the expected findings of this study can provide a new understanding of how varying levels of social presence impact user experiences in immersive technologies, thereby possibly extending the theoretical framework to encompass the complexities of the Metaverse workplace.

Finally, the study's innovative integration of TAM, DIT, and SPT can provide a fresh perspective on the interaction between individual-level technology acceptance and societal-level diffusion processes. Therefore, by exploring public beliefs and sentiments, influenced by both cognitive and emotional factors, impact the adoption and spread of the Metaverse workplace, this research aims to pave the way for new insights that challenge the conventional isolated application of TAM, DIT, and SPT, emphasising the importance of a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics that influence technology acceptance and diffusion in the context of emerging technologies such as the Metaverse workplace.

3. Methods

3.1. Data collection

We conducted a study to identify public opinions about Metaverse workplaces by using a big-data approach. Our research was reviewed for ethical compliance and was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) at St. John's University. The IRB determined that informed consent was not required since the online comments were public. Nonetheless, we took further ethical precautions by anonymising all data and removing any personal information.

We gathered data from YouTube videos posted between January 2020 and October 2023, a period marked by significant technological advancements and increased public interest in the Metaverse (e.g. Mahmoud, 2024b). This timeframe was selected to capture the most up-to-date public opinion. We opted for YouTube as the platform because of its extensive and diverse user base, which provides access to a wide range of opinions and perspectives (Cho et al., 2023; Iannitchi et al., 2023; Mahmoud, 2024a, 2024b; Mahmoud, Fuxman, et al., 2024; Savolainen, 2022; Teng, Jiang, & Khong, 2022). The searches were conducted from within two major English-speaking countries, the United Kingdom and the United States, where YouTube has a substantial user base (Statista, 2024a). This geographical diversity allowed for some control over the platform's location-based algorithm, which customises search results based on several factors, including location, language preferences, and user viewing history, where users in different countries might see different videos, even when searching for the exact keywords. YouTube is accessible in over 100 countries, supports 80 languages (YouTube, 2024), and has over 2.5 billion monthly active users as of April 2024 (Statista, 2024b). In 2022, it was one of the most downloaded mobile entertainment apps worldwide, with 154 million downloads from global users (Apptopia, 2023). Recent data (Statista, 2024a) highlights the diversity of YouTube's user base, with India leading with 476 million users, followed by the United States with 238 million users, Brazil with 147 million users, and Indonesia with 139 million users (Statista, 2024a). Other notable countries include Mexico, Japan, Pakistan, Germany, and the United Kingdom. This global reach provided a rich and diverse dataset for our study (Statista, 2024a).

The keywords used in this study were carefully chosen based on their frequency and importance when identifying the videos. We conducted a content analysis of the latest Metaverse workplace discussions and conducted extensive searches on YouTube to ensure that the data we

collected accurately represented the current trends. As a result, we used specific search keywords (e.g. metaverse workplace, working in the metaverse, metaverse office, metaverse for business, metaverse meeting, meta workrooms, horizon workrooms, meet in VR, etc.). These videos had been sorted based on their view count to ensure relevance and broader impact. Subsequently, using an API obtained from YouTube (Google), YouTube users' comments were scraped from 26 popular (based on the number of views and comments). In total, our initial dataset comprised 6982 comments.

To prepare the textual data for analysis, and in line with ensuring the highest quality of data for analysis, pre-processing and cleaning methods were applied using Python coding (see Appendix 1, Appendix 2 and Appendix 3) to remove duplicate comments, filter out non-English comments, and eliminate meaningless or incomprehensible statements (e.g., spam), thereby ensuring that our dataset was representative and free of noise. This process narrowed the dataset to 2804 comments suitable for qualitative analysis. Since our study was based on scraping publicly available data on social media, demographics were not available to us, a common limitation in social media research (e.g. Nemes & Kiss, 2021).

3.2. Data analysis—thematic analysis

Using NVivo 12 software, a software application widely acknowledged for its utility in managing complex qualitative data sets (Ashaye, Mahmoud, Munna, & Ali, 2023), initial codes were generated and subsequently grouped into overarching themes. The goal was to understand and uncover the structure of public beliefs concerning the Metaverse workplace. The thematic analysis followed a systematic process incorporating several labour-intensive stages to ensure validity and reliability, incorporating dual coding, multiple iterations, inter-coder reliability assessment, and third-party validation. Initially, a random subset of 200 comments was selected for exploratory analysis to identify potential themes. These emergent themes were used to establish a coding framework informed by both the preliminary examination and relevant literature.

Two independent researchers engaged in the coding process, contributing to the minimisation of individual biases and enhancing coding reliability (Saldaña, 2021). In the initial stage of open coding, researchers generated a range of codes inductively from the raw data. These codes encapsulated key ideas, patterns, and emerging themes relevant to public perceptions of the Metaverse workplace. These initial codes included the terms “Resolution, field of view,” “Typing, tracking, controllers,” “Eye strain, headaches,” “Can't replace PC/laptop,” “Privacy concerns, data collection,” and “Flexibility, accessibility, remote work.” These were subsequently organised into a shared codebook, which was updated iteratively throughout the research process to account for the complexity and dynamism of the data (Hack-Polay, Mas, Mahmoud, & Rahman, 2022; Thomas, 2016). Data saturation was reached after analysing approximately 29 % of the dataset (813 comments), after which no substantial new themes emerged, thereby ensuring the comprehensiveness and validity of our analysis (Guest, Bunce, & Johnson, 2006). Following the open coding stage, axial coding was performed to explore interrelationships among the initial codes. This stage was instrumental in clustering codes into broader, more abstract categories. Subsequently, selective coding was employed to refine these categories into overarching, interpretative themes that constituted the primary focus of our study (Corbin & Strauss, 2015).

Inter-coder reliability was assessed using Cohen's Kappa coefficient to ensure consistency in the coding process (MacPhail, Khoza, Abler, & Ranganathan, 2015). Any instances of disagreements between coders were resolved through discussions. Cohen's Kappa (κ) was calculated using the formula: $\kappa = (Po - Pe) / (1 - Pe)$, where Po is the relative observed agreement among coders, and Pe is the hypothetical probability of chance agreement. This calculation helped us determine the extent to which the agreement between the coders surpassed what

would be expected by chance alone (e.g. Law, Lin, Ye, & Fong, 2023). The final Cohen's Kappa score of 0.863 indicated substantial agreement between the coders (Cohen, 2016; Landis & Koch, 1977).

Moreover, validation was performed by a third coder reviewing a random sample of data. Their feedback was integrated through a consensus meeting, which helped refine the coding framework and added another layer of rigour to the findings. Also, 472 comments did not clearly fall under any of the identified themes as they expressed outlier perspectives and did not have enough context to categorise. Ultimately, the identified themes were interpreted in light of existing literature, aligning findings with theoretical frameworks and highlighting avenues for future research (Boyatzis, 1998; Elo et al., 2014; Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2016).

3.3. Data analysis—sentiment analysis and emotion analysis

For the analytical framework, the refined dataset was analysed using the Sentiment Intensity Analyzer (SIA) based on the VADER lexicon (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014) from Python's Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK). The VADER lexicon was selected for its proven efficacy in capturing the sentiment in social media texts, making it suitable for the public comments in our dataset (Hossain & Rahman, 2022). It is also robust in understanding the sentiment expressed through idioms and emoticons, which are frequent on online platforms (Banik, 2023). Each comment was assigned a compound score that served as an aggregated measure of its sentiment polarity. The compound score was used for the classification criteria to classify the comments into ‘Positive,’ ‘Negative,’ and ‘Neutral’ categories based on predefined thresholds (>0.05 for Positive, <-0.05 for Negative, and between these ranges for Neutral).

For the lexical choices, the emotion analysis employed a predefined list of emotion words grounded in seminal theories like Paul Ekman's basic emotions (Ekman, 2008) and Plutchik's Wheel of Emotions (Plutchik, 1980). The comments were tokenised, and each token was compared against this emotion lexicon. For frequency analysis, frequencies of each emotion were tabulated to assess the overall emotional tone of the public discussions on YouTube regarding working in the Metaverse. Finally, the results were visualised using Matplotlib, generating a bar chart for emotion frequencies and a pie chart for sentiment distribution. A word cloud was also produced to offer a qualitative snapshot of the corpus.

4. Results

4.1. Thematic analysis

4.1.1. Theme 1: Benefits of flexibility and accessibility

The first theme, the *benefits of flexibility and accessibility*, focuses on the positive aspects of Metaverse technology, particularly in terms of its ability to enhance workplace flexibility and accessibility (e.g. Aufegger & Elliott-Deflo, 2022; Fereydooni & Walker, 2020; Giusino, Bowman, & Toscano, 2021; Purdy, 2022). The comments reflect a growing appreciation for the potential of virtual reality (VR) technologies to create more adaptable and personalised work environments, especially for remote work.

A recurring theme in the comments is the appreciation for the flexibility that VR technology offers, especially for those working from home or in small spaces (e.g. Chen, 2023; Park et al., 2023). For example, one user shares, “I use it every day for work. My home office is small and I can't accommodate. I do wish it had more resolution but it's good enough.” This comment stresses the value of the Metaverse in maximising limited physical space, allowing users to create virtual work environments that go beyond their physical limitations (e.g. Allam, Sharifi, Bibri, Jones, & Krogstie, 2022; McGill, Kehoe, Freeman, & Brewster, 2020; Mittal, Karre, & Reddy, 2021; Selzer, Larrea, & Castro, 2022).

The potential for the Metaverse to enhance certain types of work is

also highlighted (e.g. [Yaqoob, Salah, Jayaraman, & Omar, 2023](#)). An art production team member states, *"I work in an art production team from home. I found it to be usable but it needs more resolution. Even a bump of percent would help."* This indicates that VR technology, with improvements in resolution, could significantly benefit creative fields by providing a more immersive and detailed work environment.

Another aspect emphasised is the personalisation of the workspace that the Metaverse allows (e.g. [Hopkins, 2023](#); [Jones, 2023](#)). A user enthusiastic about writing shares, *"I could really use this for writing. I could have my own writing room thanks to this."* The ability to create a bespoke virtual environment tailored to individual preferences and needs is seen as a major advantage of VR technology in the Metaverse.

The convenience and portability offered by the Metaverse (e.g. [Bibri & Jagatheesaperumal, 2023](#); [Cheng, Wu, Chen, & Han, 2022](#)) are also noteworthy. One user notes, *"I want a physical keyboard and mouse but I could put a headset on and I would SEE a monitor and the keyboard and mouse would control it. So instead of a big PC and Monitor, you can carry a good gaming setup in your backpack."* This suggests that the Metaverse can offer a compact, portable solution for work, reducing the need for bulky hardware.

Furthermore, the use of technologies empowering the Metaverse (e.g. VR/AR) for multitasking and efficiency (e.g. [Jim et al., 2023](#); [Xi, Chen, Gama, Riar, & Hamari, 2023](#)) is highlighted. A user comments, *"I would love to be able to use Virtual with a phone and small keyboard. I could use on a bus or wherever I need to quickly and effectively use multiple screens."* This illustrates the potential for the Metaverse to facilitate work in various settings, enhancing productivity and multitasking capabilities.

The privacy aspect of Metaverse workspaces (e.g. [Chen, 2023](#); [Qamar, Anwar, & Afzal, 2023](#)) is also appreciated, as one user points out, *"I use my quest virtual triple screen working on stocks. Eyes are tired. But the quality of privacy while on own working space is the best that I can experience."* This indicates that the Metaverse is seen to be able to offer a private and distraction-free environment, which is highly valued in today's open and often crowded workspaces.

In summary, the comments under this theme suggest a growing recognition of the benefits that Metaverse and VR technologies can bring to the workplace. These benefits include enhanced flexibility, the ability to personalise and adapt workspaces, portability, and improved privacy. While acknowledging the need for technological improvements, particularly in resolution, users express optimism about the potential of VR to transform their work experience, making it more adaptable, efficient, and tailored to individual needs. This theme highlights the evolving nature of workspaces and the role that emerging technologies like VR can play in shaping the future of work.

4.1.2. Theme 2: Concerns over health effects

The second theme, *concerns over health effects*, explores the health concerns surrounding the prolonged use of Metaverse headsets in the workplace (e.g. [Bale, Ghorpade, Hashim, Vaishnav, & Almaspoor, 2022](#); [Bérastégui, 2024](#); [Kim, Yang, Lee, & Lee, 2023](#)). The comments from users predominantly focus on immediate physical reactions such as eye strain, headaches, nausea, and general physical discomfort, as well as potential long-term psychological effects like mental fatigue and stress, showcasing a significant concern for the well-being of users in Metaverse environments.

A prevailing concern among users is the immediate discomfort and sickness experienced while using VR headsets (e.g. [Pons, Navas-Medrano, & Soler-Dominguez, 2022](#); [Sadia Suhail, Medha, & Meghana, 2022](#); [Sokołowska, 2024](#)). For instance, one user's comment, *"I feel sick already only wearing this gear for 5 minutes... it's going to be even more stupid in real life,"* highlights the instant physical reactions some individuals face, casting doubt on the feasibility of extended use in a work setting. Another user echoes a similar sentiment, stating, *"I tried it a few times... always felt nauseous after using it for a while."* These experiences suggest that for some, the physical side effects of VR are immediate and significant, posing a major barrier to the adoption of the

Metaverse in professional environments.

Eye strain and visual discomfort are also major concerns (e.g. [Hein, Rauschnabel, Hassib, & Alt, 2023](#); [Kim, Hwang, Kwon, & Lee, 2022](#)). One user directly addresses this, saying, *"The biggest issue I find so far is indeed the EYE STRAIN problem. My eyes hurt badly after using this thing for a while."* This indicates a fundamental issue with the current design of VR headsets, which could limit their use over long periods. Another comment, *"Its delusional think you could wear this for a day It's so bad for your eyes to do that,"* further reinforces this concern, questioning the long-term viability of using such devices in a daily work context.

Physical discomfort and strain from wearing the headsets for extended periods (e.g. [Daşdemir, 2023](#); [Kim et al., 2023](#); [Xi et al., 2023](#)) are repeatedly mentioned. A user notes, *"Your face would have marks and your neck would have pain,"* indicating the physical toll of wearing these devices. Similarly, another user states, *"I don't think I can handle a headset over my head for several hours because I can't even stand glasses."* This highlights the potential for physical discomfort and the exclusivity of the technology for those who might already have sensitivities to wearing such equipment.

The suitability of these headsets for individuals with glasses (e.g. [Laine & Lee, 2024](#)) is another point of contention. *"Another major hiccup with the headset is it does not do well with people with glasses,"* a comment that signifies the exclusionary nature of the current headset designs, potentially alienating a significant portion of the potential user base.

Aside from physical discomfort, there are broader concerns about the psychological effects of prolonged VR use in the Metaverse workplace (e.g. [Henz, 2022](#); [Sadia Suhail et al., 2022](#)). One user speculates, *"I think virtual reality makes the person mentally sick Am i right,"* indicating a worry about the mental health implications of immersive VR environments. This is a critical aspect that needs more exploration, as the psychological impacts of long-term VR use are not yet fully understood.

Moreover, the comments reflect a general dissatisfaction with the current state of VR technology in terms of resolution and weight (e.g. [Al-Ghaili et al., 2022](#); [Chen, 2023](#)). For instance, one user says, *"I tried this. It's terrible. The screen resolution isn't good enough. And the headset is too heavy."* This not only speaks to the comfort issue but also to the technological advancements needed to make VR a feasible option for Metaverse workplace settings.

Synthesising these narratives, it becomes evident that while the Metaverse offers exciting new possibilities for workplace environments, there are significant health concerns that need to be addressed. The issues range from immediate physical discomfort and potential long-term health effects to ergonomic design challenges and the suitability of the technology for a diverse range of users. These concerns underline the necessity for further research and development to create VR headsets that are not only technologically advanced but also user-friendly and health-conscious, ensuring they can be comfortably and safely integrated into everyday professional use.

4.1.3. Theme 3: Data privacy and corporate control fears

The third theme, data privacy and corporate control fears, represents the growing worry about the Metaverse workplaces' implications for personal data privacy and the increasing control of large tech corporations (e.g. [Caragnano, 2023](#); [Charamba, 2022](#)). The remarks indicate a profound doubt about the motives and actions of these companies, mainly in regard to their data collection and privacy violations.

A predominant concern is the fear of pervasive data collection by tech companies (e.g. [Bibri & Allam, 2022](#); [Renieris, 2023](#)). One user articulates this unease: *"when they dont lie they collect data and they collect a lot of data I was so disappointed when they bought I wait until the patent or someone else something better..."* This comment underscores the cynicism regarding the motives of large tech firms, hinting at a reluctance to embrace technologies that might infringe on personal privacy.

The notion of corporate control and the potential misuse of power are also significant concerns (e.g. [Egliston & Carter, 2021](#); [Zaki & Santo, 2022](#)). As one user expresses, *"In fact they have it already rather than boost*

these in and going broke already by trying to capture and not really vision They are just trying to maintain the control they already have one that will be far more corruptible than anything we have seen already from all their." This view suggests a deep mistrust in these corporations' intentions, fearing that the Metaverse could become a tool for exerting greater control over individuals.

The integration of personal accounts with VR technology, particularly with specific tech companies (e.g. Hawkins, 2022; Popescu et al., 2022), is another point of contention. A user states, "I still think forcing quest to have a [Facebook] account is a good idea I think the Quest is a great headset but I might look at [another brand] now because I don't want a [Facebook] account." This highlights the discomfort with the idea of being compelled to link personal social media accounts with VR devices, raising concerns about data privacy and the potential for misuse.

Some users express a general scepticism towards the Metaverse and its associated technologies, perceiving them as part of a larger, more ominous plan (e.g. Anidjar, Packin, & Panezi, 2023; Auerbach, 2023). One comment reads, "when you have Economic Forum people who help prop these up talking about how were all useless and we will be in verse and on to be kept happy you start to catch on to that's been the whole plan I mean they lit say it now." This reflects a fear of being controlled or manipulated through these new technological platforms.

There is also a concern about the erosion of physical interactions and the natural world (e.g. Chan, Qiu, & Xie, 2023; Sheridan, 2022), as one user ponders, "Could the same argument be made for [Metaverse]? Will lead to us living in [virtual reality] because they require us to move our [bodies] where as with [brain interfaces] we would not need to move our [bodies]." This reflects a deeper worry about the potential for VR and other immersive technologies to detach individuals from physical reality and enable greater control over their experiences.

Despite these concerns, some users see practical applications for the Metaverse in their work (e.g. Pandey et al., 2024; Zaralli, 2024), like one who comments, "I use it every day for work. My home office is small and I can't accommodate. I do wish it had more resolution but it's good enough." This illustrates the balancing act between embracing new technologies for their benefit and being wary of the potential risks they bring.

Combining these remarks, it is apparent that while there is recognition of the potential benefits of Metaverse technologies in the workplace, there is a significant undercurrent of fear regarding data privacy and corporate control. Users are wary of the intentions behind these technologies and are concerned about the potential for increased surveillance, loss of privacy, and overarching control by large tech corporations. This theme highlights the need for robust privacy protections and transparent practices by these corporations to gain the trust of potential users and ensure the ethical development and deployment of Metaverse technologies in professional environments.

4.1.4. Theme 4: Scepticism over readiness and practicality

The theme of *scepticism over readiness and practicality* reveals a significant level of doubt among the public regarding Metaverse workplaces. This scepticism is rooted in concerns over the current state of Metaverse technology and its ability to disrupt traditional workplaces (e.g. Deng & Matthes, 2023; Seo, Yoon, Kim, & Oh, 2022). It resonates with a broader societal 'teclash,' as identified by Messeri (2024), where the public's wariness towards new technologies influences their expectations and acceptance of the Metaverse. The discourse is rich with user comments, each highlighting specific issues and painting a vivid picture of the practical limitations and unresolved issues faced by early adopters of this technology.

A user's struggle with visual clarity in virtual reality (VR) (e.g. Zhang et al., 2023) is evident in their comment: "I tried working in VR with my quest for couple days But the text is so blurry to read." This statement underscores the challenge of engaging effectively in the Metaverse, where basic readability is a hurdle, indicating a significant barrier to seamless integration into professional settings. Such concerns are amplified by the broader teclash, which reinforces public caution and

scepticism towards adopting new technologies (Messeri, 2024). Another user succinctly sums up the current inadequacy of the technology: "it at present it not very good to replace a in any instance," further highlighting the gap between expectation and reality.

The concern about the Metaverse as a workplace is palpable in another user's comment: "I think it like a horrible idea I really hope this doesnt happen." This sentiment is echoed by someone who compares it unfavourably to existing technologies: "This tech ready for this use case A dual or triple real monitor set up is better and way way [more practical and efficient]."

The practicality of the current Metaverse setup is further questioned by a user who tried it and found a significant downside: "I tried this setup once and the big downside is just that text i not as clear as on a real display." This comment reflects a common concern about the quality of the virtual environment compared to traditional setups (e.g. Corpodean, Tudosă, & Popescu, 2022; Ljungholm, 2022).

The broader context of teclash intensifies these concerns, as users are not only comparing current technologies but are also influenced by a growing scepticism towards new technological advancements (Messeri, 2024). A user highlights the limitations of available productivity apps and the trade-offs between quality and functionality: "Even a bump of 50 percent would help Another huge problem is the productivity apps available I used Immersed and Virtual Desktop had the worst quality but better latency Immersed had better quality but basic functionality." This observation points to the need for more advanced and versatile applications within the Metaverse.

The lack of support for basic tools like a virtual keyboard (e.g. Bendigeri & Devaraj, 2023; Yuan Zhu & Lin, 2023) is a major obstacle, as one user notes: "One massive problem is the lack of virtual keyboard support." This limitation underscores the practical challenges in adapting current work processes to the Metaverse. The discomfort associated with VR headsets is a common theme, as expressed by a user: "You can do it but I rather work on two small monitors than deal with the headset." This preference highlights ergonomic concerns and the need for more user-friendly interfaces.

Despite these criticisms, some users see potential in the Metaverse for remote work, as one states: "I think this was a better explanation of the capabilities and the feasibility of working in it if you work remotely than what Meta provided." This comment suggests that, with further development, the Metaverse could offer unique advantages for remote work scenarios. Another user, contemplating remote work, finds some reassurance: "As someone who is going to be staring to work remotely soon I think this make me feel a bit less concerned about whether it would work for me."

The search for unbiased reviews reflects the general uncertainty: "Thanks I was failing me when trying to find reviews on it as a solution to work with my computer and various programs." The expectation of future improvements is captured in another comment: "It promising a virtual keyboard on the desk like a must have until they have higher resolution." This anticipation of technological advancements reveals a hope for a more conducive Metaverse environment for work (e.g. Narula, 2022; Sheridan, 2022).

Some comments reflect a broader concern about the direction of technology and society (e.g. Cooke, Dickmann, & Parry, 2020; Henz, 2022; Schmitt, 2023): "I find it quite concerning that there is so much effort to make the Multiverse and appealing we must look inside ourselves if we are to move forward as a this future we are moving towards is unsustainable." These philosophical considerations indicate a deeper reflection on the societal implications of adopting such technology. Even users who have tried to adapt to the Metaverse for professional purposes acknowledge its limitations: "I forced myself to use the Quest Pro every day for around I work in an art production team from home I found it to be usable but it needs more resolution." This personal experience sheds light on the current technological shortcomings and the potential for future improvements.

The gap between the marketing of the Metaverse and its actual utility (e.g. Gómez-Zarà, Schiffer, & Wang, 2023) is highlighted: "I doubt this is

gonna be anywhere near as seamless intuitive or useful as they make it seem absolutely for productivity.” This scepticism towards the marketing narratives suggests a mismatch between expectations and reality. The importance of comfort is emphasised: “I mean it like a good idea until you have to wear it for I mean it very cool from the outside Now I just want to make sure comfort is not an issue.” This focus on user comfort highlights a crucial aspect often overlooked in the rush to adopt new technologies.

Users also comment on the impracticality of the technology in its current state: “I mean the marketing is great but in real life this is not productive in the Its and not to business.” The ergonomic challenges are starkly outlined: “I really dont see with being better than a keyboard and mouse your arms have no where to rest you have to have a blindfold on pretty much.” These ergonomic issues raise questions about the long-term viability of such technology in everyday work scenarios.

Yet, there is a sense of optimism about the future of remote work and its benefits: “I really do think it that much of a ways off I think advancement surpass most people And if we can reduce traffic and need for office we save the stressfully unnecessary time spent sat in traffic reduce strain on public transport decrease pollution free up space for more housing and just generally make life easier.” Despite the prevalent cautious scepticism that most comments express, there is a hopeful outlook that contrasts with it. While acknowledging the potential for improvement, a note of caution accompanies it, “I see the benefit but the tech is just not there I tried this setup once and the big downside is just that text i not as clear as on a real display i guess we have to wait another before it there.”

Finally, a user speculates on the broader impact of the Metaverse: “I think this technology will really replace the mobile and I think this technology will soon be very nice We will no longer have just the and we bring our keyboard and mouse everywhere with us.” This perspective envisions a future where the Metaverse becomes an integral part of daily life and goes beyond current technological limitations (e.g. Adhiatma, Nurhidayati, & Fachrunnisa, 2023; Darwish & Hassanien, 2022; Hawkins, 2022; Popescu et al., 2022).

In synthesising these comments, it is clear that while there is an acknowledgement of the Metaverse’s potential, the prevailing sentiment —shaped in part by techlash— is one of scepticism regarding its readiness and practicality as a workspace. The discussions range from specific technical challenges to broader ergonomic and societal considerations, painting a picture of a technology still in its infancy with respect to its application in professional environments. Concerns range from the quality of the virtual experience to ergonomic challenges, highlighting significant gaps that need to be addressed before the Metaverse can be widely adopted for professional use.

Table 1 displays the comment frequencies and their corresponding percentage for each theme identified. They are sorted in descending order, i.e. from the most frequent to the least. Meanwhile, Fig. 1 visually represents the overarching themes.

Table 1

Themes, number of comments, percentage frequency.

#	Theme	Number of comments	Percentage frequency
1	Benefits of flexibility and accessibility	852	37 %
2	Concerns over health effects	612	26 %
3	Data privacy and corporate control fears	476	20 %
4	Scepticism over readiness and practicality	392	17 %
	Total	2332	100 %
	Uncategorised comments	472	
	Total	2804	

Fig. 1. Thematic analysis results.

4.2. Emotion and sentiment analyses

Figs. 2, 3 and 4 illustrate the findings of the sentiment, emotion and word cloud analyses, respectively. The sentiment and emotion analyses of public commentary regarding working in the Metaverse reveal an overwhelmingly positive outlook, with contentment, curiosity, and excitement being the most prevalent reactions. Over half of the sentiments expressed were favourable, reflecting enthusiasm for the potential benefits and innovations of a virtual work environment. However, while optimistic on the whole, analyses also uncovered notable concerns, as evidenced by emotions like nervousness and jealousy, alongside negative sentiment from over a fifth of responses. This suggests realistic assessments of current technological limitations and uncertainty over potential implications. The word cloud mirrors the dichotomy of optimism and caution, with future-focused terms indicative of positivity alongside references to issues and problems which likely relate to health, technical, and integrative challenges. Overall, these findings showcase

Fig. 2. Sentiment analysis results.

personalisation and adaptability that enhance the user experience and drive adoption. Moreover, the flexibility and accessibility of the Metaverse workplace resonate with the idea of *relative advantage* and *compatibility* from the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2010), indicating that these aspects are seen as improvements over current work environments and compatible with the needs of remote workers. Additionally, these benefits reflect an increased sense of social presence, as the ability to personalise and adapt virtual environments can enhance feelings of being connected and present with colleagues, thus extending SPT (Short et al., 1976) by demonstrating its relevance in immersive virtual workplaces.

Concerns over health (e.g. Bale et al., 2022; Bérastégui, 2024; Kim et al., 2023) effects constituted the second theme, where users expressed worry about the prolonged use of VR headsets, including eye strain, headaches, and physical discomfort. This theme touches on the *complexity* dimension from the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2010), suggesting that if a technology is perceived as complex or difficult to use, its adoption may be hindered. However, the findings extend this notion by highlighting that health concerns, rather than just complexity, can significantly impact the perceived ease of use and adoption of the Metaverse workplace. From the TAM perspective (Davis, 1989), these health concerns could negatively impact the perceived ease of use and potentially the perceived usefulness of the Metaverse as a workplace, thus affecting its acceptance. From the perspective of SPT, health-related discomfort can reduce the sense of presence and immersion, thereby challenging the theory's application in contexts where physical well-being is compromised. This suggests that for social presence to be effective in virtual environments, ergonomic and health factors must be adequately addressed.

The third theme, *data privacy and corporate control fears* (e.g. Caragnano, 2023; Charamba, 2022), highlighted worries about personal data privacy and the influence of large tech corporations within the Metaverse. This theme is closely related to the *observability* and *trialability* aspects of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2010), where concerns about privacy and control may limit the opportunity for potential users to experiment with or observe the benefits of the metaverse workplace without fearing for their data privacy. The findings challenge the traditional focus of DIT on innovation characteristics, emphasising the importance of considering broader societal concerns like privacy and corporate control in the diffusion process. According to TAM (Davis, 1989), such concerns could severely impact the perceived ease of use and trust in the technology, influencing its acceptance and usage. Regarding SPT, the fear of data privacy breaches can detract from the sense of social presence, as users may feel less secure and less willing to fully engage in virtual interactions. This indicates that a strong sense of social presence in the Metaverse requires robust data privacy measures to ensure user trust and comfort.

Lastly, scepticism over readiness and practicality (e.g. Deng & Matthes, 2023; Seo et al., 2022) revealed doubts about the current state of metaverse technology and its capability to replace traditional workplaces effectively. This theme is indicative of the *trialability* and *observability* facets of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2010), suggesting that people are hesitant to adopt the metaverse workplace due to uncertainties about its practicality and effectiveness. The findings extend DIT by highlighting that for emerging technologies like the Metaverse, the lack of clear use cases and proven benefits can hinder adoption, even if the innovation characteristics are promising. In TAM terms (Davis, 1989), this scepticism can be seen as a barrier to recognising the Metaverse's usefulness and ease of use, potentially slowing its adoption process. For SPT, the practical limitations and technical shortcomings can undermine the immersive experience, reducing the overall effectiveness of social presence in these virtual settings. The techlash (Messeri, 2024) also contributes to the scepticism observed in public discourse about the Metaverse's readiness. This suggests that achieving a high social presence in the Metaverse workplace requires addressing these practical and technical issues to ensure a seamless and

engaging user experience.

In addition to the thematic analysis results, the sentiment and emotion analyses showed that the Metaverse workplace elicited diverse perceptions, with over 50 % expressing positive sentiments corresponding to positive emotions like contentment, curiosity and excitement, while neutral and negative reactions made up over a fifth each. These findings address the second research question. From the lens of TAM (Davis, 1989), the positive sentiments and recognition of benefits can be interpreted as indicators of high perceived usefulness and ease of use, which are pivotal for the acceptance and adoption of new technologies. Conversely, the concerns and negative emotions, likely to be associated with health risks, data privacy, and practical utility issues, mirror the perceived barriers that can hinder this acceptance. Similarly, from the perspective of the Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Rogers, 2010), the enthusiasm and openness towards the benefits of Metaverse workspaces resonate with the innovation characteristics of *relative advantage* and *observability*. However, the worries about health, privacy, and utility highlight the significance of addressing such *innovations' perceived complexity, compatibility, and trialability* to nurture wider adoption. In terms of SPT, the positive sentiments related to feelings of connection and engagement indicate a high level of social presence, which is crucial for user satisfaction in virtual environments. However, negative sentiments related to privacy and health concerns suggest that these issues can detract from the sense of presence, highlighting areas where SPT needs to consider additional factors influencing user experience in immersive settings.

The findings contribute to TAM, DIT and SPT by revealing the emotional dimensions that shape technology acceptance and diffusion. The study shows that beyond cognitive assessments of usefulness and ease of use, affective factors like excitement, curiosity, fear, and scepticism play a crucial role in shaping attitudes towards the Metaverse workplace. This emotional layer adds depth to our understanding of the psychological factors driving technology adoption.

Therefore, our research questions were addressed by structuring a comprehensive framework of multifaceted public beliefs while also characterising the shades in sentiment and emotions using thematic, sentiment and emotion analyses. The findings align with previous observations on the tensions between promising innovations and societal worries over emerging technologies (e.g. Kuk, Faik, & Janssen, 2023; Vrščaj, Nyholm, & Verbong, 2020). Eventually, our research not only confirms that people balance optimism and caution when deciding to adopt new technologies, but it also sheds light on the emotional factors that influence this decision-making process. The study's unique synthesis of TAM, DIT and SPT offers a holistic perspective on the interplay between individual-level technology acceptance and societal-level diffusion processes, highlighting the need to consider both cognitive and affective dimensions in the context of emerging technologies like the Metaverse workplace. Moreover, by examining the role of social presence, this study challenges and extends SPT, emphasising the need to address health, privacy, and practical utility concerns to enhance the immersive experience and ensure user satisfaction in virtual work environments.

5.1. Practical implications

Our findings show that the transition to Metaverse workplaces presents both exciting opportunities and pressing challenges for businesses. To capitalise on the benefits while mitigating the risks, leaders must take a balanced, action-oriented approach.

Business leaders should recognise the significant potential of the Metaverse to enhance flexibility, collaboration, and employee engagement. For example, virtual offices can be customised to suit individual preferences and work styles, boosting productivity and job satisfaction. The Metaverse also enables seamless remote collaboration, reducing the need for physical travel and office space. Leaders should also focus on developing customisable virtual training programmes and

implementing virtual wellness activities, such as yoga or meditation sessions, to maintain high morale. A virtual recognition and rewards system can further enhance employee engagement.

However, leaders must also proactively address employee concerns. To mitigate health risks, companies should invest in ergonomically designed VR equipment and establish clear usage guidelines. This includes developing transparent VR usage policies and offering VR orientation and onboarding for new hires. For instance, they could implement mandatory break schedules, limit daily VR exposure, and provide adjustable headsets, a measure that shows consideration and respect for employees' physical needs. Designing virtual team-building activities and setting up a virtual innovation lab can further support employee well-being and creativity. Regular health check-ins and employee feedback sessions will help identify and resolve issues promptly. Conducting regular virtual town halls keeps employees informed and engaged.

It is crucial that data privacy concerns are given top priority. To address these concerns, companies should put in place strong security measures such as end-to-end encryption and strict access controls. Additionally, investing in VR accessibility features ensures inclusivity for all employees while developing a Metaverse-specific code of conduct helps maintain a positive virtual environment. Transparent data handling practices, appointing a dedicated privacy officer, and conducting regular audits will help ensure compliance with regulations and build trust with users and customers.

Customisation and personalisation are critical for successful adoption and engagement in virtual workspaces. HR and workplace strategists should collaborate closely with IT to create immersive environments that meet diverse employee needs and preferences. Offering a variety of virtual office layouts, enabling avatar personalisation, and integrating gamification elements can enhance motivation and teamwork. Understanding how different individuals work and providing them with the tools and environments that best support their productivity and collaboration is essential.

In the same way, and particularly relevant for operations and IT managers responsible for integrating new technologies into existing workflows, change management is critical, especially given the scepticism around the practicality and utility of Metaverse workplaces and the expected commitment needed for reassuring teams and easing the transition. Operations and IT managers should implement a phased rollout, provide detailed training, and offer ongoing support, starting with pilot projects in specific departments. For instance, they could provide customisable virtual workspaces, offer gamified learning modules, establish virtual onboarding sessions, and launch a dedicated helpdesk for technical issues. Introducing virtual co-working spaces and regular feedback loops and ensuring leadership visibility within the Metaverse can further ease adoption and enhance collaboration across teams.

Moreover, the multidisciplinary approach is not just important; it is crucial for addressing the complex challenges of Metaverse workplaces. It is a call for unity and collaboration. Innovation teams need to bring together experts from technology, design, ergonomics, legal, ethics, psychology, and user experience. Each discipline has a unique role to play, and their collaboration is the key to success. The role of ethics in this collaboration is particularly significant. It guides the decisions and actions of the team, ensuring that the virtual environments created are not only technologically robust and human-centric but also ethically sound. For example, cross-functional task forces can be established to develop guidelines for responsible data use, create inclusive avatar options, and design intuitive user interfaces. Additionally, ensuring accessibility by involving disability advocates, developing cybersecurity measures with the help of experts, and creating virtual governance structures to manage community interactions effectively are equally important. Involving environmental scientists can also be beneficial in evaluating the sustainability of virtual operations, while cultural experts help maintain diverse and respectful environments.

Continuous technological advancement is vital for overcoming current limitations and ensuring the long-term viability of Metaverse workplaces. Technology developers are at the forefront of this advancement, and their role is integral. They should focus on improving visual quality, reducing latency, and enhancing haptic feedback to create more immersive and comfortable experiences. Their work is not just about technology but about creating a better working environment. They should also prioritise interoperability and integration with existing systems to facilitate smooth adoption. Enhancing AI-powered personalisation to tailor experiences for individual users, investing in energy-efficient solutions to reduce environmental impact, and advancing voice recognition and natural language processing for more intuitive interactions are vital areas for development. Integrating scalable infrastructure, stronger security protocols, and better accessibility features will further solidify the Metaverse's role in future workplaces.

Prioritising the psychological well-being of employees in Metaverse workplaces is crucial. While the long-term mental health effects of extended VR use are not yet fully understood, companies can take proactive steps to support employee well-being. For example, they could provide mental health resources, encourage work-life balance, and nourish a culture of open communication and support. Introducing virtual mental health days, creating relaxation and mindfulness spaces within the Metaverse, and providing ergonomic support tools can help manage stress. Regular check-ins with employees can help identify any emerging psychological concerns and allow for timely interventions. Establishing virtual peer support groups, offering mental health training for managers, and developing personalised well-being dashboards to monitor and promote mental health are further steps that can support employee well-being.

Moreover, organisations should invest in research to better understand the psychological impacts of Metaverse workplaces. This could involve collaborating with academic institutions or mental health professionals to conduct longitudinal studies on the effects of VR use on employee well-being. Developing specific VR mental health metrics, creating employee feedback loops, and designing VR environments with psychological safety in mind will provide actionable insights. The findings from such research can inform the development of evidence-based guidelines and best practices for promoting psychological health in virtual work environments.

Ultimately, taking a proactive, multifaceted approach that balances the benefits and risks of Metaverse workplaces, organisations can create virtual environments that enhance productivity, collaboration, and employee well-being. Pilot testing VR mental health interventions, such as exploring the potential of gamification for well-being in virtual workspaces, are further steps that can guide this process. This requires a commitment to continuous improvement, employee engagement, and evidence-based decision-making. As the Metaverse continues to evolve, so too must the strategies and practices of organisations seeking to harness its potential.

5.2. Research implications

Like other studies, the current comes with some limitations that can inform future research endeavours. First, while rigorously performed, it is important to note that using YouTube videos and comments as the primary source of data might have led to biased representations of perspectives. Given that searches were conducted from the United Kingdom and the United States, the algorithm's location-specific features may have influenced the search results, as YouTube personalises content based on location, language preferences, and user history. This could result in different search outcomes for users in other regions or with different histories. YouTube's algorithm sorts content based on user interests (Kumar, 2023), potentially favouring videos that appeal to early adopters and those already interested in the metaverse. As a result, the analysed responses may be limited in their representativeness to the beliefs and sentiments of the general public, highlighting the impact of

the potential bias. Despite YouTube's diverse user base, it is important to acknowledge that demographic information such as age, gender, or professional background was not accessible due to the nature of the study relying on publicly available social media data. This limitation should be considered when interpreting the findings. Expanding the data sources to include a broader spectrum, such as professional networks, forums, and surveys, can enrich the research with diverse perspectives. Future research could employ targeted sampling methods or collect demographic information through surveys to ensure a more comprehensive representation of diverse perspectives. Messeri's (2024) work highlights the importance of understanding these differences, as techlash is not uniform but varies across cultures and regions, influencing how different populations may accept or reject the Metaverse. Indeed, the potential for a techlash against the Metaverse itself indicates a significant area for future research.

Additionally, the overall backlash against technology companies and the metaverse itself, as described by Messeri (2024), may have influenced the sentiments expressed in the comments. This techlash highlights the need for future research to consider the broader societal context and public perceptions when examining the adoption and impact of Metaverse technologies in the workplace. Furthermore, the rapid evolution of VR/AR technologies empowering the Metaverse, which poses a challenge to the study's longevity. To remain relevant, continuous research must adapt to technological advancements, exploring the ever-changing landscape of virtual work environments. Moreover, the potential oversight of cultural and regional differences in the study suggests a pivotal area for future research. Comparative analyses across various demographics could unveil new insights into global perceptions of VR/AR in the workplace.

Health and ergonomic concerns associated with prolonged VR/AR usage emerged as significant issues, indicating a need for future studies to delve into ergonomic solutions and the health impacts of these technologies. Collaborating with health professionals to guide and motivate scholarly inquiries could provide a deeper understanding of how to mitigate these risks. Additionally, the study's findings on data privacy and corporate control raise ethical considerations, highlighting the importance of future research focused on developing robust privacy protection frameworks for VR/AR work environments. Addressing these concerns is crucial for enabling trust and fostering security among users.

The scepticism regarding the practicality and readiness of VR/AR technologies for professional use to empower Metaverse workplaces revealed a gap between current capabilities and workplace needs. Investigating strategies for integrating these technologies into existing work practices could bridge this gap, facilitating a smoother transition to virtual workspaces. Furthermore, the study's infancy stage in exploring the public's beliefs and sentiments towards Metaverse workplaces calls for longitudinal quantitative research to assess the long-term impacts of these virtual environments on productivity, work-life balance, and societal norms. Understanding these long-term effects is essential for shaping the future of work. Importantly, building on our findings to develop and validate measurement models and scales to assess user experiences, satisfaction, and well-being in Metaverse workplaces can also provide a foundation for future quantitative studies.

Lastly, the psychological and social implications of extended VR/AR use in Metaverse work settings warrant further exploration. Investigating how these technologies affect social connections, collaboration, and mental health can provide valuable insights into the human aspects of virtual workplaces as an integral part of the digital transformation of firms. Conducting in-depth qualitative studies, such as interviews and focus groups, can shed light on the lived experiences of individuals working in Metaverse environments and identify potential challenges and support needs. Such research is fundamental for ensuring that the transition to virtual work environments supports not only productivity but also the well-being of individuals.

Future research may also consider building upon other theoretical frameworks to anchor their findings, such as the Unified Theory of

Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), which integrates premises from TAM and DIT (Venkatesh et al., 2003). However, in that case, while UTAUT could provide a broader understanding of technology acceptance, it does not explicitly address the relational and emotional aspects of technology use that are central to SPT. Therefore, integrating UTAUT with SPT in future studies on Metaverse workplaces could offer a more rounded examination of the cognitive, social, and affective.

Together, these interconnected research paths offer and establish a roadmap for future studies, addressing the limitations of the current work and paving the way for a deeper understanding of virtual work environments. Such that expanding data sources, conducting comparative analyses, collaborating with health professionals, exploring privacy perceptions, examining adoption factors, developing measurement scales, and investigating psychological and social implications, future research can provide a more holistic understanding of the Metaverse workplace and inform its responsible development and integration into organisational practices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ali B. Mahmoud: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104498>.

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